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**A STUDY ON SOCIAL MEDIA INFLUENCER'S MARKETING
AND ITS IMPACT ON BUYING BEHAVIOUR OF
GENERATION 'Z' CONSUMERS IN BANGALORE**

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Abstract: Social media influencer marketing has emerged as a powerful promotional strategy in the digital era, especially among Generation 'Z' consumers who actively engage with online platforms. Influencers shape consumer perceptions by sharing product reviews, recommendations, and lifestyle content through social media. This study examines how influencer marketing affects the buying behaviour of Generation 'Z' consumers and their purchase decisions. The present study examined the impact of social media influencer factors and communication sources on the buying behaviour of Generation Z consumers in Bangalore District. The findings reveal that influencer marketing plays a significant role in shaping the purchasing decisions of Gen Z consumers. The regression analysis confirmed a strong relationship between influencer characteristics and buying behaviour, indicating that factors such as opinion leadership, authenticity, credibility, visual appeal, expertise, micro-celebrity status, and transparency significantly influence consumer decisions. Among these variables, influencers who act as trendsetters and opinion leaders were found to have the strongest impact on Gen Z purchase behaviour. The study also identified that communication sources in social media marketing have a substantial influence on consumer behaviour. Dependence on digital information, influencer posts, brand reviews, information quality, entertainment value, user-generated content, and transparent communication were found to significantly affect purchase intentions. These results highlight that Gen Z consumers rely heavily on credible and engaging digital content when making purchasing decisions.

Keywords: Influencer's Marketing, Communication, Social Media, Generation 'Z', Consumer.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Social media influencers have increasingly become key actors in digital marketing strategies (Sharma, P., 2024). Influencers typically build large followings through their expertise, personality, or niche content, enabling them to significantly shape consumer attitudes and behaviours (Raja, D., et al., 2021). Among younger audiences, particularly Generation Z, the influence of social media personalities has grown rapidly. Members of Generation Z are highly connected to the internet and spend a substantial amount of time on social media platforms, which contributes to the popularity of influencers among this demographic (Ekinici, Y., et al., 2024). Generation Z, generally defined as individuals born between the 1990s and the early 2010s, tends to perceive influencers as relatable, trustworthy, and authentic sources of information, making them highly receptive to influencer recommendations (Anand, A., 2024). Due to their extensive online engagement, Generation Z is often regarded as a digitally native community, requiring marketing approaches that are specifically tailored to their preferences and behaviours (Cam, T., et al., 2024). At the same time, despite increasing investments in digital advertising, the effectiveness of traditional online promotional activities has gradually declined (Chan, F., 2022). In response to this changing market environment—where promoting products and services has become more challenging—organizations are exploring alternative ways to influence consumer behaviour (Charuvila, A., & Jnaneswar, K., 2021). One of the most prominent emerging strategies is influencer marketing. Social media platforms have transformed the way consumers interact with brands, obtain product information, and make purchasing decisions (Chatterjee, B., 2021). Unlike traditional marketing channels such as television, radio, and newspapers, influencer marketing primarily operates through social media platforms like Instagram, YouTube, and Snapchat, where influencers create authentic and engaging content aimed particularly at younger consumers (Soni, A., et al., 2024). Social media has thus evolved into a major source of information, often driven by social networks or personal interests in specific topics. In India, Generation Z constitutes nearly 33 percent of the population and represents an increasingly important consumer segment due to their strong social media presence and high level of digital literacy (Hoang, V. H., et al., 2024). This shift in trust dynamics has led to a growing reliance on influencers, with many young consumers making purchasing decisions based on influencer reviews, endorsements, and sponsored content (Batra, L., 2022). However, despite the growing popularity of influencer marketing, there remains uncertainty regarding its actual impact, the factors that contribute to consumer trust in influencers, and the way Generation Z evaluates and interprets influencer endorsements (Jose, A., et al., 2024). In the current digital landscape, influencers often have millions of followers and subscribers across various platforms (Abidin, C. 2016). As a result, organizations increasingly collaborate with these individuals to maintain a positive brand reputation and reach large audiences (Joseph, M., 2025). Influencers play a crucial role in shaping their followers' purchase intentions on social media (Burman, R., & Agarwal, D., 2023). By partnering with online influencers or social media celebrities, brands aim to expand their market reach and stimulate conversations about their products among social media users (Khandelwal, P., et al., 2024). It is widely believed that when influencers promote a product, their followers are more likely to develop an interest in purchasing it (Kutz, Kennedy O., et al., 2024).

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

The present literature review examines earlier studies on Generation Z's buying behaviour and the role of social media marketing (Lal, R., & Sharma, G., 2021). It particularly focuses on research that evaluates how different characteristics of advertising influence consumers' purchase intentions (De Vries, et al., 2017). In addition, the review highlights the growing

importance of social media platforms as effective advertising channels (Mishra, P., 2025). Generation Z's preferences are relatively well understood because this cohort was born and raised in the digital era (Pandurang, D. N., 2022). Consequently, understanding their consumer behaviour requires recognizing their strong familiarity with technology and their heavy reliance on digital sources for information (Mohiuddin, M. S., 2025). Previous scholarly studies have identified several key attributes of influencers that significantly affect followers' responses. These attributes include physical attractiveness, social presence, and homophily, which together shape the nature of influencer–follower interactions (Mulla, F., & Vaz, A., 2024). In recent years, social media influencers (SMIs) have gained increasing importance for organizations as an effective means of reaching and engaging consumers (Patel, M., et al., 2025). Influencers are often regarded as opinion leaders who use their online visibility and personal connection with followers to shape consumer preferences. An influencer can be defined as an individual who has built a large audience on social media platforms and possesses the ability to influence the attitudes, behaviours, and purchasing decisions of that audience (Pinto, P. A., & Paramita, E. L., 2021). By leveraging credibility and authenticity, influencers frequently collaborate with brands to promote products, services, or ideas through sponsored content (Chong, H. J., & Park, M. C. 2020). Many influencers also specialize in specific niches and communicate with followers through posts, videos, and other forms of digital media, creating a relationship of trust that makes their recommendations persuasive (Raj, S., 2024). Because of these characteristics, organizations increasingly rely on social media influencers as a strategic tool to interact with consumers and enhance brand communication (Rajput, A., & Gandhi, A., 2024). Influencers are widely viewed as opinion leaders whose online reach enables them to affect followers' preferences and consumption decisions. According to Randhawa, K. K. (2021), the credibility of influencers plays a more significant role in shaping purchase intentions than their physical attractiveness or level of interaction (Ahmad Al et al., 2023). For instance, research indicates that nearly 70 percent of consumers purchase products or services recommended by influencers due to their strong networking ability, which enables information about products and services to spread rapidly across social media platforms (Semwal, M., et al., 2024). Social media influencers are individuals who have accumulated substantial followings on platforms such as Facebook, YouTube, and Instagram because of their expertise, creativity, authenticity, or charisma (Shamim, K., & Azam, M., 2024). They have become a vital component of contemporary marketing strategies, particularly for companies seeking to engage younger and socially aware audiences. Sharma, A. (2022) found that Generation Z is strongly influenced by social media when making purchasing decisions. Their study revealed that influencers can significantly shape Gen Z's preferences, especially when product recommendations are presented in a personal and informal manner, such as through reviews or unboxing videos (Sidhu, L. S., & Saini, R., 2021). As a result, many brands have increasingly focused on partnerships with influencers to effectively reach younger consumers (Carrillo-Martin, A., et al., 2019). Generation Z consumers are widely regarded as digital natives who possess extensive knowledge of technology and often display skepticism toward traditional advertising methods. Their purchasing decisions are frequently based on perceptions of authenticity (Singh, D., 2024). Research suggests that many Gen Z consumers place greater trust in influencers than in traditional celebrities or conventional brand advertisements because influencers appear more relatable, transparent, and credible (Ang, L., & Wang, Y. 2021). This shift in trust has resulted in a strong reliance on influencers, with many young consumers making purchasing decisions based on influencer reviews, endorsements, and sponsored content (Soni, A., et al., 2024). Despite the growing body of research on influencer marketing, uncertainty still exists regarding its exact impact, the factors that contribute to building consumer trust, and the way

Generation Z interprets and evaluates influencer endorsements. Wielki (2020) identified three key dimensions of source credibility: attractiveness, expertise, and trustworthiness. In line with this perspective, the present study considers similarity, expertise, and trustworthiness as important dimensions of source credibility. Sharma (2024) emphasized that trustworthiness plays a crucial role in building trust in influencers' posts, particularly when influencers genuinely incorporate promoted brands into their daily lives. Similarly, the expertise of influencers is regarded as a critical element of credibility (Raja, D., et al., 2021). When followers perceive influencers as knowledgeable, experienced, and competent regarding the products they promote, they are more likely to trust branded posts shared by those influencers (Ekinci, Y., et al., 2024). Further research by Cam, T., et al. (2024) indicates that several characteristics of influencer-generated content—such as design quality, technological quality, and creativity—significantly influence the development of parasocial relationships between influencers and their followers (Bryant, J., & Kim, J. 2021). Among these factors, design quality and creativity have also been identified as strong predictors of wishful identification (Anand, A., 2024). Overall, multiple factors influence the effectiveness of influencer marketing. Elements such as trustworthiness, information quality, and entertainment value directly affect the credibility of influencers and indirectly influence consumers' purchase intentions (Charuvila, A., & Jnaneswar, K., 2021). Likewise, the purchase intentions of consumers are strongly shaped by perceptions of influencer trustworthiness and credibility (Brown, J., & Fiorella, S. M. 2019). Trust is therefore considered a fundamental factor in the success of influencer marketing strategies. According to Chatterjee, B. (2021), consumers' perceptions of an influencer's legitimacy significantly influence their attitudes toward the brands recommended by that influencer. Similarly, Soni, A., et al. (2024) identified expertise, trustworthiness, and attractiveness as the main components of credibility. Hoang, V. H., et al. (2024) further examined the impact of information quality, reliability, value, and relevance in social media marketing and found them to be key determinants of consumers' purchase intentions. In addition, Batra, L. (2022) highlighted that influencer-generated content tends to appear more personal and authentic compared to traditional promotional messages. Because Generation Z is constantly exposed to rapidly changing digital content, their attention span tends to be shorter; consequently, they prefer concise, visually engaging, and interactive formats such as Facebook videos and Instagram Reels (Jose, A., et al., 2024).

3. RESEARCH GAP

A considerable amount of research has examined the impact of influencer marketing on consumer behaviour; however, most of these studies primarily focus on a general audience or on millennials. Generation Z, on the other hand, demonstrates different patterns of social media usage and responds to influencer promotions in distinct ways. Despite this, only a limited number of studies specifically investigate how Generation Z interacts with and responds to social media influencers. One of the major gaps in existing research is the limited focus on Generation Z as a distinct consumer segment. This generation engages with social media differently from older groups, yet their reactions to influencer marketing have not been explored in sufficient depth. Additionally, many studies concentrate mainly on a single platform, particularly Instagram, while Generation Z actively uses multiple platforms such as Instagram, Facebook, and YouTube. Each of these platforms has unique features and modes of interaction, which may influence how Generation Z engages with influencers and responds to promotional content. Another limitation of current research is the lack of attention given to the factors that build trust between influencers and their followers. Although several studies discuss the reach and visibility of influencers, fewer studies examine why Generation Z trusts certain influencers more than others. Elements such as authenticity, honesty, and relatability

play an important role in shaping trust, yet these aspects remain insufficiently explored in the literature. Furthermore, much of the existing literature tends to focus on broad demographic groups while overlooking the distinctive characteristics and behaviours of Generation Z, a generation that has grown up entirely in a digital environment. There is also limited research investigating how specific factors—such as the characteristics of social media platforms and the personal attributes of influencers—affect the buying decision-making processes of Generation Z consumers. Another limitation is that many previous studies have adopted cross-sectional research designs, which provide only a snapshot of behaviour at a particular point in time. Such approaches offer limited insight into how Generation Z's interactions with influencers may evolve over time. While the available literature has contributed to understanding the relationship between Generation Z, social media, and influencer marketing, it still falls short of providing a comprehensive understanding of the cultural and contextual factors that influence this generation's behaviour. In addition, several studies rely on general, international, or broad regional data, often overlooking cross-cultural differences that may significantly influence purchasing behaviour. The specific attributes of influencers that most strongly affect Generation Z's purchase intentions also remain insufficiently examined. These gaps in the literature highlight the need for more focused research to better understand the relationship between influencer marketing and the purchasing behaviour of Generation Z consumers.

4. OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

1. To explore the impact of social media influencer factors on 'Z' Consumers buying behaviour in Bangalore District.
2. To examine the influence of communication sources on 'Z' Consumers buying behaviour in Bangalore District.
3. To provide suitable suggestions for creating social media marketing strategies by the business enterprises.

5. HYPOTHESIS

1. H01: There is no significant impact of social media influencer factors on 'Z' Consumers buying behaviour in Bangalore District.
2. H1: There is a significant impact of social media influencer factors on 'Z' Consumers buying behaviour in Bangalore District.
3. H02: There is no significant influence of communication sources on 'Z' Consumers buying behaviour in Bangalore District.
4. H2: There is a significant influence of communication sources on 'Z' Consumers buying behaviour in Bangalore District.

6. METHODOLOGY

The present study adopts a quantitative and descriptive research approach for data collection and analysis. Primary data were collected from 410 respondents, representing young adults belonging to Generation Z, including both male and female participants. A structured questionnaire was used as the main instrument for gathering the data. The questionnaire consisted of Likert-scale statements designed to measure respondents' perceptions and attitudes toward social media influencers. This method provides a systematic and efficient way to collect quantifiable data, which can be analyzed statistically to identify patterns, relationships, and trends in the responses. The study primarily focuses on evaluating numerical indicators that help in testing the proposed hypotheses regarding the influence of

social media influencers on the buying behaviour of Generation Z consumers in Bangalore District. The quantitative design enables objective analysis and supports the interpretation of the impact of influencer marketing on consumer purchasing decisions.

i) Primary data

Primary data for the study were collected using a self-administered structured questionnaire distributed to the respondents. In addition to the questionnaire, personal interviews were conducted to obtain further insights and ensure clarity in responses. The questionnaire consisted of a set of statements designed to measure respondents' opinions and perceptions. All statements were evaluated using a five-point Likert scale, with response options ranging from strongly disagree to strongly agree. For the purpose of statistical analysis, the responses were assigned numerical values: strongly agree = 5, agree = 4, neutral/can't say = 3, disagree = 2, and strongly disagree = 1. These numerical scores were used to facilitate regression analysis and other statistical techniques in examining the relationship between the study variables.

ii) Secondary Data

Secondary data for the study were collected from various reliable and scholarly sources. Information was obtained from selected peer-reviewed research articles available in well-recognized bibliographic databases such as Emerald, SAGE Journals Online, Science Direct, Scopus, Taylor & Francis Online, Web of Science, and Wiley Online Library. These peer-reviewed journals were selected due to their high academic credibility, knowledge validity, and significant contribution to the research field. In addition to these databases, secondary information was also gathered from various online electronic sources (E-sources), including published reports, academic journals, theses, magazines, research articles, and newspapers, which provided supportive background information and insights relevant to the study.

7. SAMPLE DESIGN

To obtain reliable and adequate information for the study on influencer marketing, a probability sampling technique was adopted. Probability sampling is a method in which the researcher establishes specific selection criteria and then selects respondents randomly from the population. In this sampling method, every member of the population has an equal chance of being included in the sample, ensuring fairness and reducing sampling bias in the research process.

Sampling Technique

Convenient stratified sampling is a sampling technique that combines elements of convenience sampling and stratified sampling. In this method, the population is first divided into distinct subgroups or strata based on specific characteristics or criteria in order to identify the Generation Z consumer group. Unlike traditional stratified sampling, where respondents are randomly selected from each stratum, convenient stratified sampling involves selecting participants based on ease of access or availability within the predefined strata. In this study, respondents were conveniently selected from individuals belonging to the age group of 20 to 25 years, representing Generation Z consumers in Bangalore district in Karnataka comprises 4 main geographic areas: Bangalore South, North, West and East.

Sample Size

Since the study focuses on collecting responses from male and female students as well as working individuals aged between 20 and 25 years, a purposive sampling technique was adopted. This method allowed the researcher to specifically select respondents who met the required criteria relevant to the study. Accordingly, respondents were personally approached

and requested to complete the questionnaire. After the data collection process, the final sample size was limited to 410 respondents for the purpose of analysis.

8. SCOPE OF THE STUDY

The scope of this study is confined to Generation Z consumers in India, with particular emphasis on the socio-economic and cultural context of Bangalore District. By focusing specifically on this demographic group, the study aims to examine how influencer characteristics and information characteristics influence the buying behaviour of Generation Z consumers. Accordingly, the research is limited to analyzing the impact of social media influencers on the purchasing behaviour of Gen Z consumers in Bangalore District.

9. DATA ANALYSIS—RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Linear regression analysis was conducted using IBM SPSS Statistics to examine the relationships between the study variables. The collected data were measured using a five-point Likert scale ranging from strongly disagree to strongly agree. The analysis helped determine the influence of independent variables on the dependent variable and test the proposed hypotheses.

Impact of social media influencer factors on ‘Z’ Consumers buying behaviour in Bangalore District.

H0: There is no significant impact of social media influencer factors on ‘Z’ Consumers buying behaviour in Bangalore District.

H1: There is a significant impact of social media influencer factors on ‘Z’ Consumers buying behaviour in Bangalore District.

A multiple linear regression analysis was conducted to examine the impact of various social media influencer factors on the buying behaviour of Generation Z consumers in Bangalore District.

The model summary indicates that the correlation coefficient ($R = 0.851$) shows a strong positive relationship between influencer factors and Gen Z consumers' buying behaviour. The R Square value of 0.724 implies that 72.4% of the variation in the buying behaviour of Gen Z consumers is explained by the selected influencer factors included in the model. The Adjusted R Square value of 0.716 confirms that the model has a strong explanatory power even after adjusting for the number of predictors. The standard error of the estimate (0.61978) indicates a relatively low level of prediction error, suggesting that the model fits the data well.

The ANOVA table tests the overall significance of the regression model. The F value is 94.811 with a significance level of 0.000, which is less than the standard significance level of 0.05. This indicates that the regression model is statistically significant and suitable for predicting the buying behaviour of Gen Z consumers. Therefore, the null hypothesis (H_0) stating that there is no significant impact of social media influencer factors on Gen Z consumers' buying behaviour is rejected, and the alternative hypothesis (H_1) is accepted. The coefficient table identifies which influencer factors significantly affect Gen Z buying behaviour.

Table 1: Impact of social media influencer factors

Model Summary						
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate		
1	.851 ^a	.724	.716	.61978		
ANOVA ^b						
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	400.618	11	36.420	94.811	.000 ^a
	Residual	152.884	398	.384		
	Total	553.502	409			
Coefficients ^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	1.020	.131		7.788	.000
	Visual appeal, aesthetic appearance, personal charm.	.226	.052	.223	4.341	.000
	Online visibility, digital engagement, social media activity.	.093	.048	.097	1.943	.053
	Trendsetters, thought leaders, social media authorities.	1.009	.068	.969	14.828	.000
	Trustworthiness and genuineness, reliability and sincerity.	.516	.126	.530	-4.082	.000
	Professional competence and innovation, skill and originality.	.248	.113	.224	2.192	.029
	Honesty and dependability, genuineness and credibility.	.774	.081	.793	9.585	.000
	Subject expertise, product awareness, informational competence.	.103	.093	.091	1.113	.266
	Online content exposure, digital media interaction,	.051	.062	.052	.826	.409
	Niche celebrities, internet personalities, social media stars.	.415	.082	.425	5.071	.000
	Customized brand collaborations, tailored influencer alliances.	.086	.059	.088	1.462	.144
	Honest, open and reliable; authentic, clear and dependable communication.	.139	.036	.161	3.831	.000

a. Dependent Variable: **Buying behaviour of generation ‘Z’ consumers in Bangalore**

Significant Influencer Factors (p < 0.05):

Visual appeal / physical attractiveness ($\beta = 0.223, p = 0.000$) – Influencers with attractive appearance and personal charm positively influence Gen Z buying behaviour. Opinion leadership ($\beta = 0.969, p = 0.000$) – Influencers who act as trendsetters or thought leaders have the strongest positive impact on purchase behaviour. Credibility and genuineness ($p = 0.000$) – Trustworthy and sincere influencers significantly affect consumer purchase decisions. Expertise and creativity ($\beta = 0.224, p = 0.029$) – Influencers with professional competence and creative content positively influence Gen Z consumers. Authenticity and trust ($\beta = 0.793, p = 0.000$) – Honest and dependable influencers strongly affect buying behaviour. Micro-celebrity status ($\beta = 0.425, p = 0.000$) – Influencers recognized as niche celebrities significantly impact consumer decisions. Transparency and consistency ($\beta = 0.161, p = 0.000$) – Honest and consistent communication increases consumer trust and purchase intention.

Non-Significant Influencer Factors (p > 0.05): Social presence ($p = 0.053$) – Shows marginal influence but not statistically significant at the 5% level. Influencer knowledge ($p = 0.266$) – Knowledge about products does not significantly influence Gen Z buying behaviour in this model. Exposure to digital content ($p = 0.409$) – Frequency of online content exposure alone does not significantly affect purchase behaviour. Personalized influencer partnerships ($p = 0.144$) – Brand collaborations with influencers do not show a significant direct effect.

The regression results demonstrate that several influencer characteristics—particularly opinion leadership, authenticity, credibility, visual appeal, micro-celebrity status, and transparency—have a strong and significant influence on the buying behaviour of Generation Z consumers in Bangalore District. Overall, the model confirms that social media influencer factors play a crucial role in shaping the purchase decisions of Gen Z consumers.

Table 2: Influence of communication sources on ‘Z’ Consumers buying behaviour in Bangalore District.

H0: There is no significant influence of communication sources on ‘Z’ Consumers buying behaviour in Bangalore District.

H2: There is a significant influence of communication sources on ‘Z’ Consumers buying behaviour in Bangalore District.

(0.40848) indicates a relatively small prediction error, suggesting a strong model fit. The ANOVA table evaluates the overall significance of the regression model. The F value is 227.819 with a significance level of 0.000, which is less than the threshold value of 0.05. This confirms that the regression model is statistically significant and suitable for explaining the relationship between communication sources and buying behaviour. Hence, the null hypothesis (H_0) stating that there is no significant influence of communication sources on Gen Z consumers’ buying behaviour is rejected, and the alternative hypothesis (H_2) is accepted. The coefficient results reveal which communication source factors significantly influence Gen Z buying behaviour.

Significant Factors ($p < 0.05$)

Dependence on online information / digital sources ($\beta = 0.550$, $p = 0.000$) This factor has a strong positive influence, indicating that Gen Z consumers rely heavily on digital sources when making purchasing decisions. Reliance on internet-based content ($\beta = 0.121$, $p = 0.027$) Online information plays a meaningful role in shaping consumer purchase behaviour. Influencer social media posts ($\beta = 0.215$, $p = 0.004$) Regular posts and updates from influencers significantly affect the buying decisions of Gen Z consumers. Brand reviews and product recommendations ($\beta = 0.196$, $p = 0.000$). Influencer reviews and endorsements positively influence purchase intentions. Information quality and reliability ($\beta = 0.399$, $p = 0.000$). Accurate and credible information significantly enhances consumer trust and purchase decisions. Entertainment value of content ($\beta = 0.499$, $p = 0.000$) Engaging and entertaining influencer content strongly motivates Gen Z consumers to consider products. User-generated content ($\beta = 0.245$, $p = 0.000$) Content created by consumers or followers also has a positive influence on buying behaviour. Transparency and disclosure ($\beta = 0.189$, $p = 0.001$) Honest and transparent communication by influencers positively affects consumer trust and purchasing behaviour.

Table 2: Influence of Communication Sources

Model Summary						
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate		
1	.934 ^a	.873	.869	.40848		
ANOVA ^b						
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	456.160	12	38.013	227.819	.000 ^a
	Residual	66.242	397	.167		
	Total	522.402	409			
Coefficients ^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	.095	.084		1.130	.259
	Dependence on online information, use of digital media sources, reliance on internet-based content.	.517	.040	.550	13.029	.000
	Social media posts, influencer content updates, online posts.	.107	.048	.121	2.225	.027
	Video content, visual media posts, influencer video clips.	.188	.065	.215	2.897	.004
	Digital networking platforms, online social networks, social media channels.	.077	.051	.082	1.500	.134
	Digital marketing data, online marketing analytics, social media insights.	.031	.053	.034	.591	.555
	Product evaluations, brand endorsements, product recommendations.	.190	.053	.196	3.575	.000
	Content accuracy and credibility, trustworthy information, dependable content quality.	.372	.060	.399	6.159	.000
	Content enjoyment, amusement factor, engaging and entertaining content.	.475	.051	.499	9.299	.000
	Consumer-created content, audience-generated media, community-created posts.	.056	.049	.063	1.144	.253
	Transparency and honesty, clear communication, open endorsement practices.	.226	.041	.245	5.479	.000
	Level of engagement, communication frequency, interaction rate with followers.	.174	.053	.189	3.294	.001
		.003	.023	.003	.132	.895

a. Dependent Variable: **Buying behaviour of 'Z' Consumers**

A multiple linear regression analysis was conducted to examine the influence of various communication sources in social media marketing on the buying behaviour of Generation Z consumers in Bangalore District.

The Model Summary indicates that the correlation coefficient (R = 0.934) reflects a very strong positive relationship between communication source variables and Gen Z consumers' buying behaviour. The R Square value of 0.873 shows that 87.3% of the variation in Gen Z consumers' buying behaviour is explained by the communication source variables included in the model. The Adjusted R Square value of 0.869 suggests that the model remains highly reliable even after adjusting for the number of predictors. The standard error of the estimate

Non-Significant Factors ($p > 0.05$)

Influencer video content ($p = 0.134$) – Video content alone does not significantly influence purchase behaviour in this model. Social media platforms (Facebook, YouTube, Instagram) ($p = 0.555$) – The platform itself does not significantly affect buying behaviour. Digital marketing data and analytics ($p = 0.253$) – Exposure to marketing data does not directly influence consumers. Interaction frequency with followers ($p = 0.895$) – The frequency of interaction does not significantly affect buying behavior. The regression analysis shows that communication sources play a significant role in influencing the buying behaviour of Generation Z consumers in Bangalore District. Key factors such as dependence on digital information, influencer posts, brand reviews, information quality, entertainment value, user-generated content, and transparency significantly impact consumer purchase decisions. The high R^2 value (87.3%) indicates that communication-related variables strongly explain the buying behaviour of Gen Z consumers.

10. RESEARCH FINDINGS

1. The regression model shows a strong positive relationship between social media influencer factors and Gen Z consumers' buying behaviour, with a correlation coefficient of $R = 0.851$, indicating that influencer characteristics strongly affect purchasing decisions.
2. The R^2 value of 0.724 reveals that 72.4% of the variation in Gen Z consumers' buying behaviour is explained by influencer-related factors, showing the high explanatory power of these variables.
3. The ANOVA results ($F = 94.811$, $p = 0.000$) confirm that the regression model examining influencer factors is statistically significant, leading to the rejection of the null hypothesis.
4. Opinion leadership of influencers (trendsetters and thought leaders) has the strongest positive influence on Gen Z purchase behaviour, indicating that consumers are highly influenced by influencers who guide trends and opinions.
5. Influencer authenticity and trust significantly affect Gen Z buying behaviour, showing that honest and dependable influencers are more likely to influence consumer purchasing decisions.
6. Visual appeal and physical attractiveness of influencers also significantly influence Gen Z consumers, suggesting that aesthetic appearance and personal charm enhance the persuasive power of influencers.
7. Influencer credibility, expertise, and creativity positively influence purchasing behaviour, indicating that knowledgeable and innovative influencers are perceived as more reliable sources of information.
8. Micro-celebrity status and transparency of influencers significantly impact buying behaviour, demonstrating that influencers who maintain openness and consistent communication with followers build stronger consumer trust.
9. Some influencer factors such as social media presence, influencer knowledge, exposure to digital content, and personalized influencer partnerships were found to be statistically insignificant, indicating that these variables alone do not strongly influence Gen Z purchase decisions.

10. The second regression model examining communication sources shows a very strong relationship between communication variables and buying behaviour ($R = 0.934$), indicating that communication channels play a crucial role in shaping consumer decisions.
11. The R^2 value of 0.873 indicates that 87.3% of the variation in Gen Z buying behaviour is explained by communication-related factors, highlighting their substantial influence.
12. Key communication factors such as dependence on digital information, influencer social media posts, brand reviews, information quality, entertainment value, user-generated content, and transparency were found to have a significant positive influence on the buying behaviour of Generation Z consumers in Bangalore District, while factors such as video content, social media platforms, digital marketing data, and interaction frequency were not statistically significant.

13. CONCEPTUAL FRAME WORK

14. SUGGESTIONS

1. Brands should collaborate with influencers who act as opinion leaders, as trendsetters and thought leaders have the strongest impact on the buying behaviour of Gen Z consumers.
2. Organizations should prioritize influencers who demonstrate authenticity and trustworthiness, since honest and dependable influencers significantly influence Gen Z purchasing decisions.
3. Companies should select influencers with strong visual appeal and attractive personalities, as aesthetic appearance and personal charm positively affect consumer attention and purchase intentions.
4. Influencers with high credibility, expertise, and creativity should be preferred, as knowledgeable and innovative content creators are more effective in persuading Gen Z consumers.

5. Brands should partner with micro-celebrities and niche influencers, because their close connection with follower's increases trust and positively influences buying behaviour.
6. Influencers should maintain transparency and consistent communication, including clear disclosure of sponsored content, to build long-term credibility among Gen Z audiences.
7. Marketers should focus on high-quality and reliable information in influencer content, as information accuracy and credibility significantly influence purchase decisions.
8. Brands should create entertaining and engaging influencer content, since entertainment value plays an important role in attracting Gen Z consumers and encouraging product consideration.
9. Organizations should encourage user-generated content, such as reviews, comments, and shared experiences, because it positively affects the buying behaviour of Gen Z consumers.
10. Companies should strengthen digital information channels, as Gen Z consumers heavily rely on online information and digital media sources when making purchasing decisions.
11. Influencer marketing strategies should emphasize brand reviews and product recommendations, since endorsements and evaluations by influencers significantly impact purchase intentions.
12. Marketers should adopt integrated digital communication strategies, combining influencer posts, transparent communication, and engaging content, rather than relying solely on platform presence or interaction frequency, as these alone do not significantly influence Gen Z buying behaviour.

13. LIMITATION

1. Geographical Limitation: The study is confined only to Bangalore District, which limits the generalizability of the findings to other regions of India with different socio-economic and cultural conditions.
2. Limited Sample Size: The study is based on a sample size of 100 respondents, which may not fully represent the entire population of Generation Z consumers.
3. Age Group Restriction: The research focuses only on respondents aged 20–25 years, whereas Generation Z includes a wider age range, which may affect the comprehensiveness of the results.
4. Use of Self-Reported Data: Data were collected using self-administered questionnaires, which may lead to response bias, as participants may not always provide completely accurate or honest answers.
5. Cross-Sectional Nature of the Study: The research was conducted at a single point in time, which limits the ability to observe changes in consumer behaviour or influencer marketing trends over time.
6. Limited Variables Considered: The study focuses mainly on social media influencer factors and communication sources, while other variables such as brand reputation, price sensitivity, peer influence, and cultural factors were not included.
7. Dependence on Quantitative Analysis: The research mainly uses quantitative statistical techniques (linear regression), which may not capture deeper psychological or behavioural motivations behind Gen Z consumer decisions.

8. Platform-Specific Behaviour Not Explored in Detail: Although social media platforms were included as variables, the study does not provide an in-depth analysis of individual platform dynamics such as differences between Instagram, YouTube, or Facebook in influencing buying behavior.

9. CONCLUSIONS

The present study examined the influence of social media influencer factors and communication sources on the buying behaviour of Generation Z consumers in Bangalore District. The findings indicate that social media influencers play a significant role in shaping the purchasing decisions of Gen Z consumers. The regression results reveal that several influencer characteristics such as visual appeal, opinion leadership, credibility, expertise, authenticity, micro-celebrity status, and transparency significantly influence consumer buying behaviour. Among these factors, opinion leadership and authenticity emerged as the most influential determinants, suggesting that Gen Z consumers are more likely to trust and follow influencers who demonstrate expertise, honesty, and strong personal influence. The study also identified that communication sources in social media marketing have a substantial impact on consumer behaviour. Factors such as reliance on digital information, influencer posts, product reviews, information quality, entertainment value, user-generated content, and transparency significantly affect the purchase intentions of Generation Z consumers. These findings highlight that Gen Z consumers depend heavily on credible, engaging, and informative digital content when making purchasing decisions. Overall, the results confirm that both influencer attributes and communication sources significantly affect the buying behaviour of Gen Z consumers in Bangalore District. Therefore, business enterprises should focus on collaborating with credible and authentic influencers and create engaging, transparent, and high-quality digital content to effectively reach and influence Generation Z consumers.

10. DIRECTIONS FOR THE FUTURE RESEARCH

The present study focused on the impact of social media influencer factors and communication sources on the buying behaviour of Generation Z consumers in Bangalore District. Although the findings provide valuable insights, there are several opportunities for future research to expand and strengthen the understanding of influencer marketing and consumer behaviour. First, future studies may extend the geographical scope beyond Bangalore District to include other districts of Karnataka or different regions of India. A comparative study across urban and rural areas could provide deeper insights into regional variations in influencer marketing effectiveness. Second, the sample size of this study was limited to 410 respondents belonging to the age group of 20–25 years. Future research can increase the sample size and include a broader age range of Generation Z consumers to improve the generalizability of the findings. Third, future researchers may incorporate additional variables such as brand loyalty, purchase intention, perceived risk, and consumer trust to better understand the psychological factors influencing consumer decisions. Fourth, qualitative approaches such as focus group discussions or in-depth interviews may be used to gain deeper insights into consumer perceptions toward social media influencers. Finally, future research could examine the influence of emerging digital platforms and new forms of

influencer marketing, such as nano-influencers and AI-generated influencers, to understand their impact on consumer behaviour in the evolving digital marketing environment.

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